

Role of nanotechnology in drug delivery

Abstract

The abstract delves into the pivotal role of nanotechnology in revolutionizing drug delivery systems, with a particular emphasis on the innovative concept of role of nanotechnology in drug delivery by giving an emphasis on PEGylation approach. It discusses the utilization of various nanocarrier systems such as nano-crystals, lipid nanoparticles, and PEGylated polymeric nanocarriers for targeted and efficient delivery of therapeutic compounds. The review underscores the advantages of nanotechnology, such as enhanced target specificity, controlled release, and reduced side effects compared to traditional methods. It also critiques the limitations of conventional approaches, highlighting poor biodistribution, inability to cross biological barriers without harming healthy cells, and inadequate efficacy. The review accentuates the significant strides made by nanomedicine and targeted drug delivery in addressing these challenges, with specific attention to the impact of PEGylation. Overall, the abstract underscores the transformative influence of nanotechnology-based drug delivery, laying the groundwork for future advancements in the field.

1. Introduction

The use of nanocarrier systems has become increasingly established in recent years for delivering drugs and for diagnostic purposes. This advancement has transitioned from academic research to commercial success and clinical use. The widespread availability of various nano-drug delivery systems is a clear testament to this development. Nanotechnology offers numerous advantages in treating chronic human diseases due to its ability to transport highly efficient medications in a targeted and site-specific manner. These systems effectively bridge the gap between biological and physical sciences (Patra et al., 2018).

These delivery systems are utilized for transporting a wide variety of therapeutic compounds, including chemotherapeutics, biological molecules, nucleic acids, enzymes, and peptides, to address a range of diseases and disorders. Their application is crucial in mitigating the severe side effects typically associated with anti-cancer drugs, such as organ failure, thrombocytopenia, and anemia, while achieving better target specificity and reducing required dosages. These systems are adept at traversing the body's most challenging barriers, including cell membranes and both epithelial and endothelial barriers, to deliver medications directly to intracellular sites of action. Additionally, they are designed to evade phagocytes, thereby improving treatment efficacy and reducing potential side effects (Vllasaliu et al., 2014).

Because of their small size, i.e., between 10-1000 nm, they can stay in the bloodstream longer. Additional significant benefits for drug delivery can be obtained by modifying the carrier's properties, including targeted delivery, regulated or stimuli-responsive distribution, and shielding of the treatment from biological milieus. They have controlled-release qualities due to their ability to biodegrade, the heat sensitivity of the structural elements, and pH, making them suitable for the administration of drugs or molecules (Farjadian et al., 2019). Their advantages over conventional drug systems will be explained in further sections.

Drawbacks of conventional drug delivery systems

The effective delivery of drugs to the intended location poses a significant challenge in the management and treatment of many diseases. Conventional drug delivery systems, such as oral, buccal, sublingual, rectal, and subcutaneous methods, suffer from several drawbacks including poor selectivity, inadequate biodistribution, off-target effects, large molecular size, inability to cross biological membranes without damaging healthy cells, and limited efficacy. Additionally, physiological barriers in the body, such as the blood-brain barrier, restrict the entry of active components, further hindering drug activity (Wilczewska et al., 2012). Building on these advancements, nanomedicine and targeted drug delivery present a significant leap forward. By focusing on delivering drugs directly to the affected area, these modern methods demonstrate a keen ability to mitigate the limitations observed in traditional drug delivery systems. This precision not only enhances the effectiveness of treatment, particularly in areas as critical as cancer therapy and neurological conditions but also significantly reduces the risk of side effects. Furthermore, the tailored approach of these technologies ensures that the medication remains concentrated precisely where needed, while also safeguarding it against premature breakdown. This efficiency means that lower doses of the drug are required, marking a step towards more patient-friendly treatment protocols (Farjadian et al., 2019).

2. Nanocarrier based Targeted drug delivery

Nanotechnology and nanomedicine have transformed medicine since 1980. The increasing number of nano-based medicinal compounds has led to innovative materials that can serve as therapeutic agents or deliver active components to specific cells or tissues, offering increased bioavailability, target specificity, and prolonged drug release. Using nanoparticles for medication delivery has numerous benefits over conventional methods, and creating nanoparticles using biodegradable materials allows for prolonged drug release at the target site (Singh and Lillard, 2009).

These systems are used to enhance the efficacy and reduce the undesired side effects. The commonly marketed targeted nanocarrier system includes nano-crystals, lipid nanoparticles,

PEGylated polymeric nanocarriers, nanofibers, quantum dots, liposomes, dendrimers, micelles, protein-based nanoparticles, and metal-based nanoparticles. The field of nanomedicine heavily relies on PEGylated nanocarriers (Vllasaliu et al., 2014). It is widely known that PEGylation has great potential for improving the effectiveness of nanomedicines. This review summarizes some of the PEGylated nanomedicines. These are a potential approach for designing nanocarriers for drug delivery that is currently being investigated. The review also highlights the benefits of these nanomedicines.

3. Various targeting strategies using nanocarriers

a. Passive Targeting

Passive targeting in the case of cancer tissue is mainly due to the enhanced permeation and retention (EPR) effect. The EPR effect consists of two mechanisms by which the tumor vasculature shows a leaky nature.

1. Enhanced permeation due to the increased pore size on the tumor tissue surface.
2. Increased retention of the substances in the tumor region because of the compromised lymphatic drainage system.

The EPR effect, along with the characteristic cancer features such as increased acidity and unique tumor microenvironment, can also guide the development of tumor-targeted formulations. The EPR effect leads to the increased hydraulic conductivity of the tumor tissue, enabling the easy crossing of macromolecules. The normal tissues has lesser permeability, so the formulation may not accumulate in non-tumor region (Mozar and Chowdhury, 2018). PEGylation enhances the medications' solubility, molecular mass, size, and serum stability (Mishra et al., 2016). Nanoparticles are more suitable for administration for tumor delivery because they can use the leaky vasculatures and compromised lymphatic drainage system of the solid tumors, enabling them to passively accumulate in the tumor sites specifically. This also increases the retention time of the nanoparticles inside the tumor (**Figure 1**). The PEG-modified nanoparticles possess advantages over uncoated nanoparticles, such as:

- i. Increases biocompatibility.
- ii. Lessen the biological response.
- iii. Enhanced stability.
- iv. Postponed clearance by MPS system (Wongpinyochit et al., 2015).

Figure 1 Active and passive targeting of PEGylated nanocarriers. Adapted with permission from (Shi et al., 2023) under the Attribution 4.0 International (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) © 2023 The Author(s). Published by Journal of Nanobiotechnology, Springer Nature.

The size of the drug carrier has been controlled to achieve EPR-mediated delivery of the drugs, as the size of the molecules to permeabilize the vasculature varies from 200 to 800 nm. The EPR approach for targeting the drugs to tumors requires the macromolecular drugs and the drug delivery systems to possess the property of long circulation, i.e., stay in the body for longer periods without getting eliminated, so that the drug gets accumulated in the desired targeted organ. Then, a simple approach to keep the drug at the target site is to mask it with the help of polyethylene glycol moiety or certain water-soluble polymers. **Table 1** below includes some important applications of PEG moiety for passive targeting (Torchilin, 2011).

Table 1 Important applications of PEG moiety for passive targeting.

Sr. No.	Drug substance	Spacer moiety	Use
1.	Protein and peptide macromolecules	PEG	Anti- cancer properties by saving from MPS

2.	L- asparaginase	PEG	To increase the half-life, for treatment of lymphoma and leukemia
3.	Interferon	PEG	Immuno-stimulator
4.	Anti-cancer drugs	PEG, HPMA	Cancer therapy by using paclitaxel and doxorubicin
5.	Doxorubicin	PEG	Liposomes to treat hepatocellular carcinoma and T-cell lymphoma
6.	Paclitaxel	PEG	Increase in AUC and decrease in half-life.
7.	DNA related products	PEG	Tumor-specific delivery of siRNA

The PEGylation approach for these purposes is successfully employed for liposomes, although it is thought to work with other drug carriers too. The important merit of prolonging the circulation of the drug and the carriers of the drug in the body is that it helps to maintain the desired therapeutic drug concentration at the desired site. This approach is also useful for the areas with limited blood supply and for the ligand-mediated targeting of the drug molecules. It can also help to attain a sufficient amount of the drug in the areas where it takes more time to attain the targeted concentration (Kang et al., 2020).

Challenges in the drug delivery by EPR effect:

There are some challenges in the delivery of PEGylated nano-formulations through passive targeting mode (Nakamura et al., 2016), some of them are indicated in the **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Challenges in passive targeting of PEGylated nanocarriers

b. Active Targeting

EPR effect or passive targeting of the drugs alone cannot guarantee a successful cancer treatment since the drug may not reach the desired site in in the intended or the therapeutic concentrations, leading to the therapeutic insufficiency of the drug. For active targeting strategy, the favorable thing with the cancer tissues is that the cancer cells have many receptors that are overexpressed on their surface, to meet enhanced demand of micronutrients and other factors required for the growth and survival of the cancer cells. (Russell-Jones et al., 2004).

For active targeting of the drugs, the backbones of the drug substances can be covered with a variety of ligands such as proteins, hormones, vitamins and growth factors that are recognized by the cancer cells (Nateghian et al., 2016). For the cell-specific uptake, the surfaces of NPs are coated with specific ligands that can easily recognize and bind to the cell surfaces, as shown in **Figure 1** (Gajbhiye et al., 2020a).

The drug enters the tumor cell in one of two ways, depending on the linker molecule. The first one is receptor-mediated internalization of the entire prodrug by endocytosis and subsequent degradation by endosomal/lysosomal pathway or the second way is receptor-independent internalization of the drug into targeted cells after extracellular cleavage (Mishra et al., 2016).

Table 2 Various active targeting strategies found in literature, along with the target receptors and intended use.

Table 2 Various active targeting strategies

Sr.No.	Target receptor	Ligand	Spacer	Use	Reference
1.	Several receptors	Antibodies and peptides	PLA-PEG	Targeting of thiol group containing drugs	<i>Betancourt et al., 2009</i>
2.	Microtubule receptors	Paclitaxel	PEG, PAMAM	Anti-cancer therapy	<i>Rompicharla et al., 2019</i>
3.	HER2	Adenovirus	PEG	Metastatic cancer therapy	<i>Kim et al., 2011</i>
4.	Transferrin	Several anti-cancer drugs	PEG	Cancer therapy	<i>Choi et al., 2010</i>
5.	Folate receptors	Doxorubicin	PEG	Cancer therapy	<i>McNeeley et al., 2007</i>

4. PEGylated nanocarriers and their types used for targeted drug delivery

The drugs that are given systemically need to remain in the circulatory system substantially longer to accumulate in the targeted tissues at appropriate concentrations. But proteins and peptides are quickly broken down and removed from the blood; therefore, methods for lengthening circulation duration are required. Also, the reticuloendothelial system (RES) is a significant barrier for nanocarrier systems as it clears them out before reaching at the site of the action. This system quickly removes nanoparticles from circulation, especially hydrophobic particles, which causes them to build up in the liver, spleen, or bone marrow (Vllasaliu et al., 2014). One such method involves covering the therapeutics surface using an inert polymer that prevents interactions with bloodstream constituents and gives it stealth qualities. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is the most commonly used stealth polymer for drug delivery. PEG has been included in drug delivery systems to improve the pharmacokinetic profile of both macromolecular therapies and particle formulations. This increases the stability,

biocompatibility profile of the nanoparticle along with increased capacity to infuse into the biological membranes and decreases the toxicity of drugs. PEGylation prevents aggregation, opsonization, as well as phagocytosis of nanoparticles by protecting the surface and extending circulation time (Suk et al., 2016). The diagrammatic representation of different types of PEGylated nanocarriers are shown in **Figure 3** below.

Figure 3 PEGylated nanocarriers and their types used for targeted drug delivery

a. PEGylated Liposomes for targeted drug delivery

PEGylated Liposomes as shown in **Figure 3(a)** are recognized as the most promising nanocarriers in the field of drug delivery, particularly chemotherapeutic medicines. PEGylated liposomes were used in an intriguing investigation to conceal and unmask a targeted ligand coupled to liposomes. By utilizing cysteine-cleavable phospholipid-PEG5000, it was feasible to effectively conceal folate-anchored liposomes from RES clearance, prolong their circulation, and efficiently target tumors passively. Experiments on tumor absorption in mice with artificially produced brain tumors (targeted liposomes containing DOX were administered, following a cysteine infusion) have verified the improved transport of folate-anchored targeted liposomes. *Kizelsztein et al.*, prepared PEGylated liposomes entrapped the antioxidant tempamine, which was tested for its ability to stop mice from developing experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE). According to the study, over 3% of the PEGylated liposome injection dose made it to the EAE mice's brains. The results obtained indicated that PEGylated liposomes reduced the severity and duration of EAE in the mice (*Kizelsztein et al.*, 2009).

b. PEGylated gold nanoparticle for targeted drug delivery

AuNPs have been considered the most interesting nanomaterial because of their unique optical, electronic, sensing, and biochemical properties and potentially applied for medical imaging, drug delivery, and tumor therapy in the early detection, diagnosis, and treatment (Kong et al., 2017). Smart drug delivery systems with gold nanoparticles are recent approaches for targeted therapy of life-threatening diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Stimuli-responsive on-demand release of therapeutic agents at the diseased site can significantly limit serious adverse effects (Refaat et al., 2021). Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) that have unique near-infrared (NIR) plasmon resonance are excellent agents for early-stage cancer diagnosis and photothermal cancer therapy resulting from light-induced localized hyperthermia thus leading to cell death and tumor regression (Sun et al., 2013). For cancer targeting, immobilized biomolecules like antibodies (Abs) on GNPs should retain their optimal activities, which is especially important to the active targeted imaging and therapy where the bio-conjugated GNPs can target specific cells. (Day Lissett Bickford John Slater Nicholas Riggall Rebekah Drezek Jennifer L West, 2010). Therefore, immobilization of immunoglobulins (IgGs) on GNPs by Fc region via a cofactor can yield versatile and highly efficient immunoconjugated GNPs. IgG-binding proteins like Protein-A (ProA) and Protein-G (ProG) are valuable candidates for ordered antibody-immobilization. (Sun et al., 2013), successfully anchored in immobilizing IgGs on the GNPs via PEGylation with ortho-pyridyl-disulfide-polyethylene glycol-succinimidyl valerate, (OPSS-PEG-ProG), as shown in **Figure 3(b)**, for recognizing the antigens HER 2 overexpressing breast cancer cells, SK-BR-3, were efficiently targeted and ablated at suitable laser exposure. ELISA demonstrated that ~ 75% of the anti-HER-2 Ab binding activity of ProG was retained after the PEGylation. The results showed that the cell membrane integrity loss was induced by localized hyperthermia of the GNP/light interaction when GNPs were bound to cell membranes.

c. PEGylated silver nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are considered the most significant and intriguing nanomaterials. AgNPs have received particular attention due to their potential utilization in the treatment and diagnostics of cancer and are also well utilized in antibiotic resistance. However, some bacteria often show resistance towards AgNPs. To overcome this PEGylated AgNPs are synthesized. *Zhao et al.*, synthesized stable PEGylated AgNPs loaded graphene oxide (GO) nanocomposite (GO-PEG-Ag) as shown in **Figure 3(c)**, having strong antibacterial properties, high biocompatibility, and effectiveness over time. The addition of PEG to the nanocomposite significantly increased its stability in physiological fluids. Consequently, even after

centrifugation, the GO-PEG-Ag may readily distribute in different medium, which would significantly aid practical applications. The antibacterial test findings show that the GO-PEG-Ag demonstrated potent antibacterial ability towards bacteria (*E. coli* and *S. aureus*) carrying the *mcr-1* (mobilized colistin resistance) gene encoding resistance to colistin, which is regarded as a last resort antibiotic against multidrug-resistant bacteria (Zhao et al., 2017). In one another study *Abdelfattah et al.*, constructed DOX-loaded PEGylated AgNPs and it was reported that the prepared nanoparticles showed sustained release with lesser side effects (Abdelfattah et al., 2022).

d. PEGylated dendrimer for targeted drug delivery

Dendrimer provides an ideal platform for delivery of bioactive as they represents a well-defined highly branched nanoscale architecture with specific molecular weight and available in many generations based on the layer of branches put on the core with several modifiable surface groups. However, the actual potential of dendrimer faces toxicity limitations. PEGylated dendrimer mediated drug delivery overcomes the shortcoming of dendrimer reticuloendothelial system (RES) uptake, drug leakage, and enhances the solubilization. In general, the dendrimers possess vacant internal pockets which can hold the poorly soluble cargoes. Additionally, the outer shell of dendrimers possess a wide number and variety of surface functional groups which can be conjugated or anchored with various moieties (Thakur et al., 2015). Biotin (vitamin H) has attracted great attention from pharmaceutical research. It is an essential micronutrient, which is vital for normal cellular function. Owing to high tumor specificity and rapidly proliferating malignant cells overexpress biotin to meet their biotin uptake. This specific interaction of biotin and its receptors has been explored to develop various biotin-conjugated nanocarriers to increase the uptake of anticancer drugs by various tumor cells. Rompicharla et al., 2019 develop biotin conjugated PEGylated multifunctional Poly (amidoamine) (G4 PAMAM) dendrimer system to effectively deliver paclitaxel (PTX) (Refer **Figure 3(d)**), a chemotherapeutic agent specifically to the cancer cells by following active-targeting approach. Biotin was anchored onto the surface of the dendrimers to target the vitamin uptake receptors overexpressed on the cancer cells. PTX was covalently linked to the surface of the G4 PAMAM dendrimer using a succinate linker. Further, to avoid the toxicity of dendrimers due to their cationic nature and to prolong the systemic circulation of the conjugate, PEG has been attached. In another study, Brain glioma, especially glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), a type of brain tumor, is one of such serious diseases which adversely affects the brain's anatomy and physiology. GBM-bearing brains express extensively large numbers of low-density lipoprotein receptors (LRP) on the luminal endothelial plasma membranes. Angiopep-2 is reported as a

ligand of LRP, which possesses a high brain penetration and perfusion capability in mice. Based on this theory, Parashar et al., 2018 designed Angiopep-2 anchored PEGylated Poly propyleneimine (PPI) dendrimers for targeted delivery of paclitaxel to the brain glioma by receptor mediated endocytosis (RME) . PPI dendrimers were synthesized and modified with PEG-2000 for surface neutralization. However highly positive charge at surface dendrimers can be reduced by surface modification using PEG molecules. These long circulating PEGylated PPI dendrimers alone are incapable of drug targeting and thus required to be targeted using ligand receptor interaction. PEGylated PPI dendrimers were further conjugated with Angiopep-2 (ANG-PEG-PPP) for improved drug delivery across blood brain barrier (BBB) into the vicinity of brain glioma. PTX loaded ANG-PEG-PPI dendrimers has shown a better anti-glioma effect than PTX alone.

e. PEGylated Hyaluronic acid for targeted drug delivery

Hyaluronic acid (HA), a naturally occurring polysaccharide present in the extracellular matrix alongside synovial fluids of the body. It is capable of binding to different cancer cells which over-express CD44, a HA receptor, because of this property it has been used as targeting moiety for cancer treatment. But due to the cellular uptake by phagocytic cells of RES it gets accumulated in the liver and the efficacy of HA-nanoparticles is reduced. To overcome this problem *Choi et al.*, synthesized PEGylated HA-nanoparticles labeled with cyanine 5.5 fluorescent dye. The results obtained indicated that the PEGylation of HA-NPs (**Figure 3(e)**) decreased their cellular absorption in vitro, more nanoparticles were absorbed by cancer cells that overexpressed the HA receptor CD44 compared by regular fibroblast cells. Following intravenous injections of Cy5.5-labeled PEGylated HA-nanoparticles into healthy mice, ex vivo findings of the organs utilizing optical imaging technology showed that PEGylation successfully decrease the liver uptake of nanoparticles and extended their circulation time and the brightest fluorescent signals were found in the tumor site suggesting their great tumor target ability (Choi et al., 2011).

f. PEGylated albumin for targeted drug delivery

Formulators have gained interest in human serum albumin (HSA)-based nanoparticles after the approval of paclitaxel-bound nanoparticle Abraxane® by USFDA, to treat patients with metastatic cancer of breast and non-small-cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) (Zhao et al., 2015). Albumin, nature's carrier for binding and transporting medications within the body, is suitable for use in these formulations due to its high capacity for loading nucleotides, biodegradability, non-toxicity, and consistent production procedure. Additionally, albumin is employed in gene therapy. Targeted drug-delivering approaches to tumor tissues can enhance anticancer efficacy

and reduced toxicity profile by sparing normal tissues. Recently, tumor-directed monoclonal antibodies (such as trastuzumab, cetuximab, and antiCD3), as well as other targeted ligands (including folate, RGD, and apolipoproteins), have been bound to the surfaces of albumin nanoparticles, further functionalizing them, enhancing tumor cells absorption. The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) is highly overexpressed on the surface of tumor cells. In an artificial glutaraldehyde crosslinked albumin-based nanoparticle, anti-EGFR nanobody (EGa1) was coupled to surface-coated PEG chains with this objective in mind (Kouchakzadeh et al., 2013). 17864, a multikinase inhibitor has been incorporated into the core of albumin and is maintained there by a platinum coordinative link based on Lx. Because they stop several receptor tyrosine kinases from acting, multikinase inhibitors can hinder the development, survival, and angiogenesis of tumor cells.

Study reveals that, in comparison to PEGylated nanoparticles, EGa1-PEG functionalized nanoparticles demonstrated a 40-fold higher affinity for EGFR-positive cancer cells. By clathrin-mediated endocytosis, 17864-Lx loaded EGa1-PEG nanoparticles were taken up by the tumor cells and finally degraded in lysosomes. The intracellular administration of EGa1-targeted nanoparticles successfully releases the kinase inhibitor and reduces tumor cell growth; however, non-targeted formulations had no antiproliferative effects on 14C cells (Kouchakzadeh et al., 2013).

The utilization of monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and transferrin is wide, as targeting ligands for actively targeted nanomedicine formulations. In the family of epidermal growth factor receptors, the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) is increased in the stomach, ovary, lung, and breast cancers (Tai et al., 2010). It comprises a tyrosine kinase domain inside the cell as well as an external ligand-binding domain. It might be argued that HER2 is an ideal marker for precise delivery to tumor cells because it is an accessible cell surface receptor that is overexpressed in both original tumors and metastatic locations. The anti-HER2 monoclonal antibody 1F2 recognizes the extracellular domain of HER2 exclusively. Kouchakzadeh et al., 2013 formulated PEGylated human serum albumin(HAS) nanoparticle that is linked to a thiolated 1F2 mAb and allows for the incorporation of many medicines and nucleotides. For 1F2-modified nanoparticles, PEGylation can produce the maximum cellular absorption.

According to different studies, brain endothelial cells with expressed transferrin receptors mediate the endocytosis of transferrin by the cells. Most polar nucleosides, such as azidothymidine, an HIV-1 chemotherapeutic drug, do not easily pass the blood-brain barrier. (Mishra et al., 2006) formulated transferrin-anchored PEGylated albumin nanoparticles with azidothymidine loading (Tf-PEG-Nps) (**Figure 3(f)**). By employing PEG to modify the

surface, surface-active RES interception and sequestration of nanoparticles might be prevented. Additionally, Transferrin and to create site-specific carriers for brain targeting, PEGylated nanoparticles were combined.

g. PEGylated Dextran for targeted drug delivery

Dextran, a polymer composed of glucose residues primarily connected by 1,6-bonds, serves as a drug transporter. Nevertheless, there are specific challenges associated with dextran such as high molecular weight dextran usually responsible for immunogenicity. The dextran molecule grafted with short PEG residues serves as better approach than long chain dextran as a carrier system as showed in **Figure 3(g)**. After attaching several PEG residues, the dextran core may still include free reactive groups that are ideal for the attaching or single-point modification of a variety of medicines, such as proteins and peptides, to produce their long-circulating forms. *Lukyanov et al.*, synthesized PEGylated dextran and from the biodistribution studies it was reported that Dextran's liver absorption is reduced and its circulation duration is markedly lengthened by the PEG alteration. The amount of PEG residues added determines the extension of the circulation time. Further it was concluded that the remaining reactive groups, such as amino groups, in the PEGylated dextrans make them ideal long-circulating transporters for therapeutic as well as diagnostic substance (*Lukyanov et al.*, 2004).

In another study, *Naeye et al.* synthesized PEGylated dextran nanogel for the delivery of siRNA. It was concluded from the study PEGylated nanogels were readily absorbed by HuH-7 human hepatoma cells and A431 human epithelial carcinoma cells. In addition, siRNA-loaded PEGylated nanogels significantly reduce enhanced green fluorescent protein (EGFP) levels in a human hepatoma cell line (HuH-7_EGFP) while being non-toxic to the cells (*Naeye et al.*, 2010).

h. PEGylated carbon nanotube for targeted drug delivery

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) (**Figure 3(h)**), have acquired a lot of attention in the biomedical fields since the time they were discovered by Sumio Iijima in 1991 because of their peculiar framework, and characteristics which involve high aspect ratios, sizable surface areas, rich surface chemical functionalities, and size stability on the nano-scale (*Son et al.*, 2016). A single graphene sheet can be utilized to create single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs), while multiple graphene sheets can be utilized to create multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs)(*Elhissi et al.*, 2012). Additionally, studies have been carried out and it is reported that non-spherical nanocarriers (such as CNTs) are preserved in the lymph nodes for a sustained duration as compared to the globular nanocarriers (e.g., liposome)(*Bottini et al.*, 2011; *Elhissi et al.*, 2012). The tiny nanoneedle mechanism allows easy passage of functionalized CNTs (f-

CNTs) across the plasma membrane with the help of an energy-dependent, endosomally-mediated manner. This is because CNTs can be attached with large targeting moieties to offer sustained/controlled release behavior with cellular targeting.

It is a proven technique for treating cancer by stimulating apoptosis in cancer cells with the help of mitochondrial targeting. Many cancer cells develop anti-apoptotic properties by upregulating anti-apoptotic proteins, such as B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2), Bcl-XL, and myeloid cell leukemia-1 (Mcl-1), which prolongs their continuity. Bcl-2 proteins have been a potential therapeutic target for the development of methods to eradicate cancer cells. Due to their favorable pharmacokinetic, toxic, and superior cellular internalization profiles, PEGylated Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) have been used as a promising platform for delivering a variety of drugs, including small molecules and biomacromolecules. These anti-apoptotic proteins are susceptible to be inhibited by some small molecules like ABT737. Kim et al., 2017 created a non-covalently bonded polyethylene glycol-coated carbon nanotube-ABT737 nanodrug that enhances mitochondrial targeting, and boosts the effectiveness of therapy against lung cancer. Apoptosis was brought on by the PEG-CNT-ABT737 nanodrug which was built up in the mitochondria of A549 non-small cell lung cancer cells. The proposed mechanism was abruption of mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP), lowering the expression of Bcl-2, and production of intracellular ROS generation resulting in enhanced efficacy against lung cancer. In another study by Mehra and Jain, 2015, it is stated that the nuclear hormone receptor superfamily's estrogen receptors (ERs), are overexpressed in malignant cells. After connecting specifically to each receptor by endocytosis or a tiny nanoneedle mechanism, MWCNTs tethering (Estrogen) likely distributes doxorubicin (DOX) more effectively into the malignant cells. Due to the upregulation of estrogen receptors (ERs) on human breast MCF-7 cells, estrone-anchored nanotube formulation was more readily absorbed than free DOX. Similar to this, the elevated cancer-targeting propensity of the estrone-anchored MWCNTs formulations was also validated by the pharmacokinetic and boosted anti-tumor actions.

i. PEGylated quantum dots for targeted drug delivery

The utility of quantum dots (QDs) (**Figure 3(i)**), for biological applications is predicated on stably dispersing the particles in aqueous media. However, the potential application of QDs in bioimaging is limited by their hydrophobic and toxic properties (Xiao et al., 2014). To overcome this challenge, An appropriate surface modification and polymeric encapsulation of QDs could make them water-soluble and minimize their toxicity. Polyethylene glycol is the most widely used polymer for the delivery of hydrophobic agents because of its great solubility in organic solvents, biodegradability, and biocompatibility. However, treatment strategies for

inflammatory bowel disease have been constrained by limited therapeutic efficacy and serious adverse effects owing to a lack of receptors for targeted drug delivery to the inflamed colon. Upon inflammation, CD98 is aberrantly over-expressed in colonic epithelial cells and infiltrating immune cells. Xiao et al., 2014 constructed CD98 Fab'-bearing quantum dot (QD)-loaded nanoparticles (Fab'-NPs). CD98 antibodies were digested and reduced to generate Fab'-SH. Next, NPs were coated with a hetero-bifunctional cross-linker (MAL-PEG-NHS), yielding maleimide-functionalized PEG-NPs (MAL-PEGNPs). Finally, MAL-PEG-NPs were reacted with Fab'-SH to obtain the final NPs (Fab'-NPs). *In-vitro* analyses suggested that Fab'-NPs were internalized into cells via CD98-mediated endocytosis and showed significantly higher cellular uptake efficiency

In another study, The newly discovered black phosphorus quantum dots (BPQDs) present an intriguing advantage in the field of biomedicine. Furthermore, phosphorus, which makes up approximately 1% of total body weight in humans, is an essential element that is inherently biocompatible. A BPQDs-based nanoplatfrom with drug delivery capability and triple collaborative targeted tumor therapy was designed. Wang et al., 2020 developed a novel delivery system FA (folic acid)-PEG@BPQD@ DOX for targets folate receptor (FR) in a mouse tumor model of 293T cells. Briefly, a laser was used to induce the production of reactive oxygen and heat in the BPQD, resulting in cell damage. In the meantime, the temperature was raised, and the drug was released from the nanocomposite. The BP-based drug delivery system with targeted synergistic photodynamic therapy (PDT), photothermal therapy(PTT), and chemotherapy exhibited an excellent antitumour effect in mice.

j. PEGylated chitosan for targeted drug delivery

Among all other polymeric nanoparticles, chitosan-based nanoparticles are the most effective, economical, and eco-friendly. Chitosan nanoparticles (ChNPs) (**Figure 3(j)**), have attracted a lot of attention for biomedical applications due to their cationic characteristics, electrostatic interactions, biodegradability, and biocompatibility. A biological macromolecule called chitosan has a variety of bioremediation, anticancer, and drug carrier capabilities. Numerous studies have shown that ChNPs are a potential targeted medication delivery mechanism for the treatment of cancer. Many growth factors or growth factor receptors, including the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) family, the epidermal growth factor (EGF) receptor family, and the transferrin receptor are overexpressed on the surface of tumor cells in cancer(Herdiana et al., 2021). Chitosan nanoparticles (NPs) were modified at the surface with PEG to provide stealth character and transferrin (Tf) for the active targeting function by transferrin receptor-

mediated endocytosis to promote drug delivery to cancer cells. It was discovered that cancer cells took up NP-PEG-Tf more readily than non-targeted cells.

Recent developments in monoclonal antibodies for targeted drug delivery represent a significant advancement in the biomedical profession, particularly for the treatment of breast cancer (Nag et al., 2016). To improve longer blood circulation times, higher solubility rates, better Reticuloendothelial System (RES) escape capabilities, and less antigenicity, doxorubicin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles were treated with polyethylene glycol. Additionally, labelling these nano-systems with breast cancer-specific monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) like anti-human mammaglobin (Anti-hMAM) and anti-human epidermal growth factor (Anti-HER2) has been a promising method to increase the specificity and sensitivity levels of the developed CSNPs system, potentially improving the survival rate and quality of life of breast cancer patients (Helmi et al., 2021).

5. Site Specific delivery of therapeutics

Site-specific drug delivery is the specialized form of drug delivery, in which the drug is targeted to the specific required target site in optimum therapeutic concentrations at a pre-defined rate. This avoids the possible off-target adverse effects ranging from acute to chronic effects followed by coma and death. The site-specific delivery delivers the drug through some of the following approaches,

1. Utilizing a carrier moiety in which the drug can be loaded this can be done to safeguard the drug in other parts of the body.
2. Ligand mediated targeting for release the active drug only at the desired site.
3. The drug can be chemically or physically modified for targeted release, ex. Prodrug approach (Hassanzadeh, 2021).

The site-specific delivery of the drugs can be done by using PEGylation strategy for various disorders such as:

a. Brain disorders

In the fight against deadly brain diseases, targeted drug delivery via the blood-brain barrier (BBB) is a challenging task. The main obstacles include rapid blood flow, RES absorption, and nanocarrier excretion. PEGylation has proven to be beneficial for the targeted delivery of drugs to the brain. It is generally known that PEGylation can lengthen the period that nanocarriers remain in the bloodstream by preventing RES uptake, which is essential for enhancing the uptake of nanocarriers into the brain. For the targeted delivery of the molecules that bind to the brain, PEGylation also serves as a linker. This carrier system is used to deliver proteins,

peptides, and drugs of high molecular weight to the brain (Gajbhiye et al., 2020b). For example, brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is important for CNS repair but exogenous BDNF is restricted by BBB and for its efficient delivery. *Xing et al.*, synthesized transferrin conjugated BDNF loaded PEGylated liposomes coupled with either a glial fibrillary acidic protein promoter (pGFAP) or cytomegalovirus promoter (pCMV) to distribute this molecule through the BBB. Both liposomal formulations show exceptional potential for BBB crossing. Additionally, the pGFAP group showed higher levels of BDNF expression in the cerebral cortex in comparison to the pCMV group. This study provided preliminary support for the targeted administration of BDNF by medication to the brain (Xing et al., 2016). PEGylated dendrimers are also employed for targeted brain delivery. *Santos et al.* used various generations of cationic poly (amido amine) (PAMAM) linked with PEG for the treatment of stroke. BBB model's integrity was maintained in *in-vitro*, and rat primary astrocytes or bEnd.3 (bEnd.3 is a mouse brain cell line derived from BALB/c mice) cells weren't affected negatively by PEGylated dendrimers no cytotoxicity was observed. After 24 hours of injection, PEGylated dendrimers were found in the ischemic cortex neurons of animals suffering from focal brain ischemia, demonstrating the ability to serve as a delivery method during stroke (Santos et al., 2018).

b. Cancer

The PEGylation approach can be used for tumor suppression. The extent of the PEG coating required for the tumor accumulation has been clearly stated by *Mozar et al.*, Low density PEGylation creates a "mushroom state", (**Figure 4**), that experiences increased opsonization (engulfment of any foreign material, xenobiotics, or biomolecules by opsonin proteins) and cellular absorption and can eventually demonstrate higher tumor accumulation and enhanced intra-tumor medication effectiveness. However, a denser PEG results into less opsonization and cellular uptake ultimately resulting in less intratumor accumulation (Mozar and Chowdhury, 2018).

Figure 4 Formation of low- density "mushroom state" by PEG moiety

In one study *Guo et al.*, reported the effectiveness of 2,3-dimethylmaleic-anhydride-poly(ethylene glycol)- ϵ -poly-L-lysine-doxorubicin /lapatinib polymeric (DMMA-P-DOX/LAP) nanoformulation against breast cancer. After being released from DMMA-P-DOX/LAP the DOX and LAP significantly reduced the tumor in MCF-7 (breast cancer cell line) model and the penetration of active drug inside the tumor tissues was effectively enhanced (*Guo et al.*, 2020). *Xin et al.*, synthesized paclitaxel (PTX) loaded methoxy poly(ethylene glycol)-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (MPEG-PTMC) nanoparticles and investigated for their potential anticancer properties against glioblastoma multiform . The concentration of PEGylated nanoparticles was significantly increased in the brain tissues after the 12 hours of administration. The survival rate in the animals treated with MPEG-PTMC was higher than the other groups (*Xin et al.*, 2010).

c. Inflammatory disorders

Inflammation is the first response of the body's immune system, excessive or persistent inflammation causes chronic inflammatory diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis and inflammatory bowel disease (*Cao et al.*, 2015). Activated macrophages greatly influence in initiation, maintenance, and pathogenesis of this disease by producing several pro-inflammatory cytokines. Suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines and mediators from activated macrophages has been investigated as a key strategy for the treatment of inflammatory diseases. There are many DMARDS (Disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs) are used for treatment. However, Lack of efficacy and drug-related adverse effects are important reasons for the discontinuation of this treatment in patients with inflammatory diseases. *Chandrasekar et al.*, 2007 synthesized folate-targeted poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) conjugates of anionic poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) generation 3.5 dendrimer (G3.5 PAMAM) loaded with indomethacin as targeted drug delivery systems to inflammation. The conjugates revealed that approximately 7, 11, and 20 folate-PEG moieties were attached to each molecule of G3.5 PAMAM dendrimer. Drug loading was significantly increased in the folate PEG conjugates when compared with the nonconjugated dendrimer. The folate-PEG conjugates had shown reduced uptake by RES organs, and in particular, the exposure to the stomach was nearly one-tenth of the nonconjugated dendrimer, indicating limited gastric-related side effects.

d. Bone disorders

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a chronic and irreversible degenerative disease. Characterized by synovial inflammation and cartilage destruction (*Xiong et al.*, 2021). Although many clinical therapeutics like nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), glucocorticoids (GCs), and other drug treatments are one of effective strategies for OA, there are still some shortcomings

that need to be overcome such as frequent injection, gastrointestinal, cardiovascular risks, and potential overdose. Formononetin (FMN) is a phytoestrogen purified from natural herbal plants (e.g., *Astragalus membranaceus*, *Trifolium pretense*). It was reported to have pharmacological effects including anti-inflammatory, capacity by suppressing IL-6 and TNF- α in neuroinflammatory rats and effectively antagonized proteoglycan loss through decreasing the expression of Matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-3, MMP-13, and attenuating oxidative stress. However, the bioavailability of FMN is low because it has poor water solubility and can hardly penetrate through the dense matrix of cartilage. Besides, with lacking specific targeting, FMN may be rapidly cleared in the joint. Sometimes, the retention time after intra-articular (IA) injection is short and repeated articular injection is inevitable. Thus, it is imperative to increase the water solubility and cartilage-targeting effect of FMN to improve its pharmacological effects.

e. Blood disorders

Hemophilia A and B involves decrease in the coagulation factors such as factor VII which results in prolonged bleeding. PEGylation approach helps to prolong the half-life of drug or drug loaded carriers in the blood. The brand name 'Esperoct' includes factor VIII in glyco-PEGylated form for the treatment of hemophilia A was found to be increased in its half-life by 1.6 times (Zhou et al., 2015). Apart from that, PEGylated nanocarriers have their application in leukemia. Here PLGA has been modified by use of methoxy Poly(ethylene glycol) (mPEG) to modify its hydrophilicity and to prepare stealth nanoparticles which could avoid, or at least reduce, the uptake by phagocytes and prolong drug residence time in blood circulation. Nanoparticles prepared from PEG modified PLGA have been extensively investigated as drug carriers due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and ability to provide controlled release. After intravenous administration, the PLGA-mPEG nanoparticles were reported to remain in the systemic circulation for hours, whereas the PLGA nanoparticles were removed from blood within few minutes. The PEG layer provides a steric barrier to the particle and reduces their opsonization, thereby making them long circulating. Against this background, the present investigation was aimed at developing long circulating, Cyt loaded PLGA-mPEG based biodegradable nanoparticles which would have sustained release (Yadav et al., 2011).

6. Various Stimuli for efficient drug delivery through the nanocarriers

To improve drug delivery specificity, efficacy, and biological activities, stimuli-responsive nanocarriers have been logically conceived and developed while considering various pathological profiles in normal tissues, intracellular compartments, and tumor microenvironments. Overall, the stimuli that the nanocarriers could respond to were the

following: internal stimuli like pH, ATP, H₂O₂, enzyme, redox-potential, and hypoxia; external stimuli like magnetic field, temperature (i.e., thermal), ultrasound, light (i.e., laser), and electronic field (**Figure 5**). The stimuli-sensitive functions make it easier to release drugs on demand or under control, promote site specific accumulation, activate drugs or probes, expose ligands, activate nanoparticles, convert charges, signal in particular locations, detect unique pathological factors or molecules, thus is widely used in theragnostic. Furthermore, external forces, or stimuli, may also be able to alert nanocarriers to changes in their biological performances. For instance, an external magnetic field may cause a tumor's magnetic nanocarrier accumulation to rise. Additionally, the stimuli might be used to activate specific prodrug-formulated nanocarriers biologically in sick areas or cells to provide precision therapy (Mi, 2020).

Figure 5 Representation of different stimuli-responsive multifunctional nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery applications. Adapted with permission from (Majumder and Minko, 2021) under the attribution of Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>) © 2020 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

7. Conclusion

The conclusion underscores critical advancements in targeted drug delivery, spotlighting PEGylation's role in refining drug carriers like dextran, carbon nanotubes, and quantum dots for enhanced therapeutic efficacy. This modification notably minimizes immunogenicity while

extending circulation, facilitating precise delivery to target cells, notably cancerous ones. The capacity for specific modifications heralds a leap in developing focused, side-effect-sparse treatments. The findings encapsulate the promise of PEGylated nanocarriers in surmounting cancer therapy challenges, hinting at a significant shift towards their clinical adoption. Continued innovation in this sphere is anticipated to revolutionize treatment modalities, offering renewed hope in healthcare.

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